

THE DEVELOPMENT OF NON-PERSONAL FORMS IN THE HISTORY OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation: In most languages, impersonal forms of the verb are distinguished, that is, those that is not used as a predicate, but may be part of it. The impersonal forms of the verb do not have grammatical signs of person, number and mood, do not express the time of the action (present, past or future), but only indicate the correlation in time, that is, whether the action expressed by them is simultaneous with the action of the predicate or precedes it. Impersonal forms of the verb are not the same in all languages. For example, in Russian there is a gerund, which is not in English, and in English there is a gerund, which is not in Russian. The topic was chosen in order to study in more detail the non-finite forms of the English verb, the non-finite forms can be described from a non-traditional point of view.

Key words: infinitive, gerund, impersonal forms of verbs, part of speech, English, function, history.

A verb is a part of speech (class of words) that calls an action (to run, to read, to read, to speak) or representing various states, relationships, manifestations of signs (to love to love, to know to know, to see to see, to be, to belong, to redden blush).

In the language system, the verb occupies a special place that is not characteristic of any other part of speech: all statements are formed on the basis of the verbal member, which represents the described situation.

The verb is an open class of words, that is, its composition can be unlimitedly replenished with new lexical units. This process, which lasted throughout the known history of the English language, is very intense at the present time.

This article discusses the impersonal forms of the English verb:

- ❖ Infinitive
- ❖ gerund
- ❖ Participle

It also discusses the features of expressing the temporal relations of their non-personal forms.

Impersonal verb forms in modern English include participle, gerund, and infinitive forms. The analysis of these forms is of interest from the point of view of the general characteristics of the structure of the modern English language,

one of the specific features of which is a developed system of non-personal forms and the peculiarities of their use. The impersonal forms of the verb have both verbal and nominal features.

Zhigadlo V. N. [2p. 141] notes that the verbal features of non-personal forms are:

1) Characteristic of them, although having their own characteristics, categories of time, type and pledge

2) The ability to accept an unpredictable addition and be determined by the circumstance. This ability finds its expression in combinations of the same type, which do not differ from similar combinations with personal forms of the verb. Thus, verbal features are manifested in the presence of non-personal forms of the English verb in the category of tense, aspect, voice, as well as in the characteristics of phrases in which the studied forms function:

Reading a book aloud – without reading a book aloud – to read a book aloud – I am reading a book aloud

The infinitive, which is an impersonal form of the verb, being an integral part of the English verb system. The infinitive exists in many languages, in particular in Russian. In terms of meaning, the English infinitive is identical to the Russian one - it combines the features of a verb and a noun, but differs from the Russian infinitive in its morphological and, partially, syntactic features. The properties of a noun are that in a sentence the infinitive can perform the same functions as the noun.

If the infinitive is in the modal verbal predicate, and, therefore, it is preceded by a modal verb, the latter itself is an indicator of the infinitive, since the modal verb without the subsequent infinitive can only be used in a structural representation; but this usage is always anaphoric, and consequently in the previous part of the text the modal verb was followed by the infinitive:

I can't be bothered now to wrap anything up

– Neither can I old boy

The unconditional indicator of the infinitive, which is noted by all researchers, is the particle *to*: *to go иду, to write писать, to learn учиться*

As Guzeeva K.A. writes. [1] (2000, 51), sometimes the particle *to* expresses the infinitive itself. This is mostly seen in spoken English when the infinitive *to* ends a phrase (usually in a response).

The only impersonal form of the verb that has no analogue in Russian. Like the participle I, it is formed from the infinitive with the suffix *-ing*, but at the same time it combines, along with verbal features, the signs of a noun (and not an adjective, like participle I), that is, it is similar in grammatical meaning to the

infinitive. However, the gerund differs from the infinitive not only in form formation, but also in certain features of use, due to the specifics of its compatibility with other words.

As already mentioned, the gerund combines, along with verbal features, the features of a noun.

The properties of the verb are that the gerund has the categories of aspect and voice, can have dependent words and be determined by the adverb. The properties of a noun are expressed in the fact that the gerund:

1. Can be used after a preposition

He is fond of reading.

2. can be defined by a possessive pronoun and a noun in the possessive or common case

He insisted on my leaving at once.

As Ilyish B.A. writes (1980, 215), all impersonal forms of the verb differ in one characteristic feature: the category of time has not an absolute, but a relative meaning. In other words, the time expressed in each of these forms does not have a meaning in itself, but only in relation to the time of the personal form of the verb. For example, the so-called present infinitive expresses not the present tense from the point of view of the speaker, but simultaneity with the action expressed by the personal form of the verb.[3]

He could sing means "he could sing"; the tense of the action expressed by the form "sing" in this case refers to the past, since the personal form of the verb is in the past tense.

CONCLUSION:

1. Gerund forms do not have an independent temporal meaning, but can express an action in the present, past and future tense.
2. The category of time for the gerund, as well as for the participle, is absolute, and relative
3. Indefinite forms of the gerund (reading, being read) basically denote an action that is simultaneous with the action expressed by the predicate, and depending on this, they refer to the present or future tense
4. The precedence of the action expressed by the predicate can also be expressed by combining the indefinite form of the gerund with the prepositions on (upon) and after.

Literature:

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